

The growing environmental impact of COP websites: An analysis of UNFCCC COP host country websites (1995–2025)

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Overbrowsing is an applied research group advancing sustainable web practices

overbrowsing.com

Digitalisation's promise of dematerialisation has not yet materialised

UNCTAD

<https://unctad.org/publication/digital-economy-report-2024>

ICTs produce 1.5% – 3.2% of global greenhouse gas emissions

2x

ICT emissions are twice that
of the aviation industry

4th

If the internet were a country,
it would be the fourth-largest polluter

5 yrs

Just under five years to take
action to limit global warming to 1.5°C

<https://www.un-ilibrary.org/content/books/9789213589779>
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-01046-9>
<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-00177-3>

Since 2010, average desktop pages have grown by 523.2% and mobile pages by 1,700%

<https://httparchive.org/reports/page-weight?start=earliest&end=latest&view=list>

Sustainable web design: to design and implement digital services and products that that put people and the planet first

W3C

Unregulated digitalisation risks leaving people behind and worsening environmental and climate challenges, further entrenching global disparities

UN

<https://unctad.org/publication/digital-economy-report-2024>

Kidlington fly-tip

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Current tools

Live-measurement only

Current tools measure page size synchronously

<https://websitecarbon.com>
<https://cardamon.io>
<https://ecograder.com>

Can't recalculate

GHGP supports scope 3 recalculation;
CO2e models are improving

Can't contextualise

No baseline for comparison; unable to view the growth and cumulative impact

The web is ephemeral: websites are continually updated, supplanted, or vanish entirely

90%

Over the past 12 years, more than 90%
of the web has disappeared

50%

50% of web pages vanish or become
unrecognisable within a year

11,300

Lifespan of a page is roughly 11,300 days

<https://www.pewresearch.org/data-labs/2024/05/17/when-online-content-disappears/>
<https://doi.org/10.1109/JCDL.2014.6970226>

Internet Archive (Wayback Machine)

Sheldon Tapestry Map (Bodleian, Oxford University)

Wasteback Machine is a JavaScript library for analysing archived web pages, measuring their size and composition to enable retrospective, quantitative web research

Mahoney, D. (2026). Wasteback Machine: a method for quantitative measurement of the archived web. *Information Research an International Electronic Journal*, 31 (iConf), 448–464.
<https://doi.org/10.47989/ir31iConf64185>

<https://github.com/overbrowsing/wasteback-machine>

Methodology

Wasteback Machine

Using the first version of Wasteback Machine and a script to automate the study

COP host country sites

Web sphere of COP host countries had to first be identified

Selecting pages

Selected 10 pages starting from main navigation → home page key links

CO2e Emissions

Using CO2.js (Bytes to CO2e). Limitations: assumes based upon today's infrastructure

Green hosting status

Hosting status was checked using The Green Web Foundation's Green Web Check

Comparison

Findings compared against HTTPArchive State of the Web Report 2025

COP 1995-2025

Average-Max-Min chart showing changes in the mean grams of CO₂e emissions per pageview of COP host country websites (1997-2025)

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COP 1995-2025

COP Host Homepage (COP3-COP30, 1997-2025): Page Size and Resource Composition.

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COP 1995-2025

COP Host Homepage (COP3-COP15, 1997-2009): Page Size and Resource Composition.

Mahoney D, Terras M, Lee J, Zeller F (2025). The growing environmental impact of COP websites: An analysis of UNFCCC COP host country websites (1995-2025). PLOS Climate 4(11): e0000767. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000767>

COP 1995-2025

COP Host Homepage (COP16–COP30, 2010–2025): Page Size and Resource Composition.

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COP web pages emit up to 10x more carbon than average

819 t

United Nations homepage = 443 petrol cars or nearly 9 million air miles, annually

117 kg

COP29 in-session views produced 117 kg CO₂e, equal to 5–10 mature trees

10x

COP web pages emit up to 10x more carbon than average (0.36g CO₂e)

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Mahoney D, Terras M, Lee J, Zeller F (2025). Sustainable Web Design: Policy Recommendations for Mitigating the Environmental Impact of United Nations' Websites. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15625433>

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Cop climate summit websites ‘produce more carbon than average sites’

Between 1995 and 2024 when the last Cop conference was held, average emissions from the websites had risen by more than 13,000%, according to data.

Sarah Ward • Monday 10 November 2025 19:00 GMT

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Not so green after all! Websites produced for COP climate conferences emit 10 TIMES more carbon than average sites, study finds

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By XANTHA LEATHAM, EXECUTIVE SCIENCE EDITOR
PUBLISHED: 19:00, 10 November 2025 | UPDATED: 19:00, 10 November 2025

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Websites produced for COP conferences emit up to 10 times more carbon than average internet pages, according to a new study.

As this year's United Nations climate summit kicks off in Brazil, researchers have revealed a sharp increase in the carbon emissions generated by the conference's websites over time.

Analysis indicates that between 1995 – when the first Conference of the Parties (COP) was held – and 2024, average emissions from COP host websites have risen by more than 13,000 per cent.

And this year's page is set to emit the equivalent of 313kg of CO2 – the amount of carbon that would take 15 mature trees a whole year to absorb.

While the increase is partly the result of huge growth in computing power and internet use, the carbon footprint of COP sites is still significantly higher than the average.

Today's headlines: Outrage as 300 'healthy' ostriches are executed by firing squad after infectious disease claims; Scientists are baffled to discover mysterious 'voids' in the third-largest pyramid of Giza – as scans...; How to win at rock, paper, scissors: Scientist reveals the simple trick that will guarantee you beat your...; Arctic blast to freeze 155 million Americans with temperatures plunging to 15°F; Why is it so hot in the UK? Confused Brits claim it's 'a little too warm for mid-November' – as Britain...; Nothing to hide here! Humanoid robot moves so smoothly, its inventor is forced to cut it open to prove...; The definitive guide to reading facial microexpressions – from angry flared nostrils to wrinkles of fear; What could go wrong? 'Organic Tamagotchi' toy is filled with BACTERIA which children must feed to keep alive; Is heavy drinking as a teen GOOD for you? Youngsters who booze with their friends go on to earn more as...; It's not the 60+ days of Christmas! Exasperated Brits blast John Lewis, Coca-Cola, and Argos for releasing...

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COP Webpages Emit up to 10 Times More Carbon Than Average Sites

NOV 12, 2025 AT 12:57 PM EST

By Hannah Millington
11:48 AM (GMT)

Views of webpages used for the Conference of the Parties (COP) sites—referring to the annual United Nations climate change summit—emit up to 10-fold more carbon emissions than average site views.

Leaders from around the world—with the notable exception of the U.S.—are on their way to Belém, Brazil, for the 30th United Nations Climate Change Conference, COP30, which takes place from November 10 to 21. COP is the main decision-making body of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)

Researchers from the University of Edinburgh in Scotland have revealed average emissions from COP conference websites have “dramatically” risen by more than 13,000 percent between 1995 and 2024.

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Cop websites produce far more carbon than others, researchers say

Report finds that sites set up for past UN climate summits emit seven times more CO2 than global average as latest Cop begins in Belém

Adam Vaughan, Environment Editor
Monday November 10 2025, 7.50pm, The Times

The authors of the report say the United Nations should require countries hosting future summits to reduce the carbon emissions relating to their sites' page views.

The carbon emissions generated by visiting recent United Nations climate summit websites are significantly higher than those of other sites, researchers

Sustainable Web Design: Policy Recommendations for Mitigating the Environmental Impact of United Nations' Websites

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We have included [...] sustainable websites in the draft Host Country Agreement annexes

UNFCCC

COP31 Host Country Website (Antalya, Türkiye) <https://cop31.tr>

COP 1995-2026

Average-Max-Min chart showing changes in the mean grams of CO₂e emissions per pageview of COP host country websites (1997-2026)

COP 1995-2026

COP Host Homepage (COP3-COP31, 1997-2026): Page Size and Resource Composition.

Good COP, Bad COP

-70%

COP31 website is 70% smaller than the average of the previous five COP websites

+372%

COP31 homepage is 372% above the global average (0.36g CO₂e)

+9%

COP31 is not hosted on verified renewable energy according to Website Carbon

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<https://web.archive.org/web/20260604113413/https://www.websitecarbon.com/website/cop31-tr/>

<https://web.archive.org/web/20260604114157/https://www.thegreenwebfoundation.org/green-web-check/?url=https%3A%2F%2Fcop31.tr%2F>

<https://unfccc.int/documents?search3=host%20country%20agreement>

Thank you
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